

varieties. A scale for each growth stage was adapted from the Horsfall-Barrett scale based on visual estimation of tissue area infection, widely used in plant pathology. The Horsfall-Barrett scale is based on proportion of disease intensity and has 12 divisions. When it was used to rate disease based on actual lesion area, the score of 1 was excluded.

The modified scale, also based on percent lesion area, has 9 instead of 12 divisions: 1 = 1-3% lesion area, 2 = 4-6%, 3 = 7-12%, 4 = 13-25%, 5 = 26-50%, 6 = 51-75%, 7 = 76-87%, 8 = 88-94%, and 9 = 95-100%. It is suitable for scoring disease level at 11-14 DAI on plants 20-30 DAS (Table 1).

At late to maximum tillering (40-50 DAS) final disease ratings and relative ADPCs agree with each other, but not with apparent infection rates. A different scale was developed to score these growth stages at 14-17 DAI: 1 = < 1%, 2 = 1-2%, 3 = 3-4%, 4 = 5-8%, 5 = 9-16%, 6 = 17-32%, 7 = 33-40%, 8 = 41-50%, 9 = > 50%. The modified scale for plants from maximum tillering to maturity also was suitable for evaluating varietal resistance to BB (Table 2).

For the purpose of field screening, the current *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scoring is adequate to distinguish resistance from susceptibility.

Table 2. Varietal resistance to BB measured by 3 different scales. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Relative ADPC value	Leaf area infected (%)	SES scale	Modified scale (1 to 9)
IR910143-6-1	0.128	45.47	7	9
TN1	0.127	44.37	7	9
IR24	0.125	42.33	7	8
MTU18	0.110	41.90	7	8
Khao Khao Nhay	0.108	36.50	7	7
Milyang 23	0.107	33.43	7	7
RP4-2	0.104	34.87	7	7
IR8	0.098	30.43	7	6
Binirnal	0.084	30.43	7	6
CAS209	0.076	27.30	7	6
Aneira	0.074	27.12	7	6
59439 (B11/MAS)	0.065	26.80	7	6
BG94-1	0.062	24.87	5	6
Yakai	0.061	24.70	5	6
Yolle	0.057	21.83	5	6
Pyi Daw Aye	0.050	18.50	5	6
Zenith	0.049	12.67	5	5
ASE Pute Rono	0.043	15.23	5	5
Pale Angga	0.043	14.23	5	5
Band Merah	0.039	14.23	5	5
Kauk Hnyin	0.031	14.80	5	5
Ketan Jimbruk	0.030	9.20	5	5
Gaukkyi	0.027	11.40	5	5
Pae Moku	0.024	9.17	5	5
Akundi	0.015	5.47	5	4
Tahun Gembrong	0.013	4.17	5	3
Warangal Culture 1263	0.011	4.03	3	3
Meegauk	0.1010	4.03	3	3
IR20	0.008	2.60	3	3
AUS40	0.005	2.23	3	2
Sankurcha	0.009	1.80	3	2
IR22	0.004	1.33	3	2
AUS338	0.004	1.17	5	2
DZ78	0.004	1.33	3	2
IR1545	0.003	1.00	3	2
Makhmal Mehi	0.003	1.00	3	2
AUS463	0.003	0.87	1	1
DV85	0.002	0.60	1	1

Sources of resistance to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Nepal

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Blast epidemics at the seedling stage are frequent in different parts of Nepal. Varieties resistant to *P. oryzae* become susceptible within a few years. To find new sources of resistance, we reviewed varietal reactions in the International Rice Blast Nurseries at Kankai, Parwanipur, Khumaltar, and Palung 1983-85. These locations cover a wide range of climatic conditions (plain, midhill, and high hill).

Sources of broad-spectrum resistance to *P. oryzae* Cav. in Nepal.

Rice line ^a	Donor parents ^b
C1322-28	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR7473-118-2-2	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
IR9852-22-3	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR13240-108-2-2	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR17525-278-1-1 ^c	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR18348-36-3-3	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
IR18349-22-1-2	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR19672-140-2-3	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR21820-154-3-2	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
Iri 360	unknown

^a All were resistant in Kankai (plain, 1984-85), Parwanipur (plain, 1983-85), Khumaltar (mid-hill, 1983-85), and Palung (high hill, 1983-84). Scoring was done according to the Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9: 0-2 = resistant (R). ^b Extracted from *Parentages of IRRI crosses, IRI to IR50,000*. ^c Data not available for Parwanipur, 1985.

Disease pressure was high at all locations. A large number of rice lines exhibited resistance reaction in 1 or 2 tests, but only 10 lines were resistant in 2 to 3 yr at all sites (see table). Nine were progeny of Tadukan, Sigadis, and Tetep. These donor parents also exhibited resistance at all test sites.

Changes in disease reaction of several international differentials indicate the existence of different physiological races of the blast pathogen and unstable resistance in released varieties. Some of the lines identified that have desirable agronomic traits might be sources of resistance to control leaf blast epidemics at the seedling stage. □